

Institute of Pedagogy of NAES of Ukraine

Department of Monitoring and Evaluation of the
Quality of General Secondary Education

**THE USE OF EDUCATIONAL MONITORING RESULTS
IN TEACHING PRACTICE IN UKRAINIAN SCHOOLS**

Teacher Questionnaire

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Introduction

The questionnaire was developed to conduct the study “The use of the Educational Monitoring results in teaching practice in Ukrainian schools” within the framework of the research project “Methodology for Assessing the Impact of the Results of International and domestic Monitoring Studies of Education Quality on the Development of General Secondary Education in Ukraine”, carried out by the Department of Monitoring and Evaluation of the Quality of General Secondary Education of the Institute of Pedagogy of the National Academy of Educational Sciences of Ukraine. State registration number of the research project: 0126U000643. Project implementation period: 01 January 2026 – 31 December 2027.

Purpose of the study: to examine the specific features of using the results of educational monitoring studies in the professional activities of teachers in secondary schools in Ukraine.

Questionnaire

Dear colleagues,

We invite you to participate in a survey aimed at examining the specific features of using the results of external monitoring studies, both national and international, designed to assess the quality of education in the pedagogical practice of general secondary education institutions.

The responses received will be used in aggregated form for research and analytical purposes. Participation in the survey is voluntary, and responses are anonymous.

Thank you for your time!

By continuing to complete the questionnaire, you confirm that you have read the information provided, understand the conditions of participation, and give your informed consent to participate in the survey and to the use of your responses in aggregated form:

I agree that my responses to the questionnaire will be used for the stated research purposes, provided that they do not contain information that could personally identify me, in accordance with the Law of Ukraine "On Personal Data Protection" No. 2297-VI, 2010, as amended in 2024.

I. GENERAL INFORMATION

1. The region where your educational institution is located

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Vinnytsia Oblast | <input type="checkbox"/> Mykolaiv Oblast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Volyn Oblast | <input type="checkbox"/> Odesa Oblast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Dnipropetrovsk Oblast | <input type="checkbox"/> Poltava Oblast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Donetsk Oblast | <input type="checkbox"/> Rivne Oblast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Zhytomyr Oblast | <input type="checkbox"/> Sumy Oblast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Zakarpattia Oblast | <input type="checkbox"/> Ternopil Oblast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Zaporizhzhia Oblast | <input type="checkbox"/> Kharkiv Oblast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Ivano-Frankivsk Oblast | <input type="checkbox"/> Kherson Oblast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Kyiv Oblast | <input type="checkbox"/> Khmelnytskyi Oblast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Kyiv | <input type="checkbox"/> Cherkasy Oblast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Kirovohrad Oblast | <input type="checkbox"/> Chernihiv Oblast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Luhansk Oblast | <input type="checkbox"/> Chernivtsi Oblast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Lviv Oblast | |

2. Your teaching subject:

- Ukrainian Language / Literature
- Foreign Language
- Mathematics (Algebra, Geometry)
- Biology
- Physics
- Chemistry
- Geography
- Computer Science
- History
- World Literature
- Vocational Education
- Physical Education
- Art/Music
- Defense of Ukraine
- Primary School
- Other: _____

3. The level of school education at which you work:

- Primary school
- Grades 5–9
- Grades 10–11

4. Type of settlement where your school is located:

- City (population of at least 10,000)
- Town (population of 5,000 or more)
- Village (population of less than 5,000)

5. Teaching experience

- Up to 5 years old
- 6–10 years old
- 11–20 years old
- 21–30 years old
- Over 30 years old

6. Your age

- 18 - 25
- 26 - 35
- 36 – 45
- 46 – 55
- 56 – 65
- more than 60

7. Sex

- female
- male

8. Your education

- Vocational education
- Higher education
- Academic degree

9. Have students from your school participated in educational quality monitoring studies?

- Yes
- No

9a. If so, in which ones?

- Monitoring of primary education quality
- Monitoring the organization of distance learning in general secondary schools (COVID/war context)
- Nationwide monitoring study of education quality under martial law
- Monitoring study of the implementation of the New Ukrainian School (NUS) in primary schools
- PISA (OECD, Programme for International Student Assessment)
- TIMSS (IEA, Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study)
- TALIS (OECD, Teaching and Learning International Survey)
- Others: _____

10. Have you personally participated in studies monitoring the quality of education?

- Yes
- No

All subsequent questions concern any external monitoring studies and assessments of the quality of education, including students' learning outcomes, conducted at the national, regional, and international levels, hereinafter referred to as monitoring studies.

II. AWARENESS OF MONITORING RESULTS

1. How would you rate your level of awareness regarding the monitoring results?

- 1 – Not at all informed
- 2 – Slightly informed (I know about the study, but haven't looked at the results)
- 3 – Moderately informed (I have a general idea of the results)
- 4 – well-informed (I am interested in the results and know the main conclusions)
- 5 – very well-informed (I regularly review the results and participate in public discussions about them)

2. Where do you usually find out about the results of the monitoring?

- from the school administration
- from colleagues/the teaching methods association
- from professional development courses
- from official websites (Ministry of Education and Science, Ukrainian Center for Educational Quality Assessment, State Agency for Educational Quality Assessment)
- from educational media (e.g., New Ukrainian School, Osvita.ua)
- from scientific/educational journals
- from social media
- I do not receive such information

3. In what format do you usually review the monitoring results?

- Short news items/posts
- Analytical reports
- Presentations/webinars
- Discussions at faculty meetings
- Other: _____

4. Do you receive general, practice-oriented conclusions or recommendations tailored for teachers based on the results of the monitoring?

- Yes
- No

III. USING THE RESULTS IN SCHOOL PRACTICE

1. Based on your observations, at what level and how often are the results of monitoring used in school practice?

	1 never	2 very rarely	3 occasionally	4 often	5 constantly
on an individual basis (at the teacher's discretion)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
at the level of the teaching staff (necessary decisions are made following group discussions)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
at the administrative level (as decided by the school administration)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
at the national level (recommendations from government agencies, in particular, the Ministry of Education and Science, regarding specific changes to the educational process)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
None of the above; these results are generally not used	<input type="checkbox"/>				

2. For what purposes do you use the monitoring results?

- To plan review lessons on specific topics
- To provide individualized support to students
- To adapt teaching approaches
- To communicate with parents
- To evaluate my own work
- To improve my professional skills
- I do not use these results

IV. BARRIERS TO THE USE OF MONITORING RESULTS

1. What challenges do you face in your teaching practice when it comes to using monitoring results to improve the quality of teaching?

- Lack of time
- Insufficient information about monitoring results at the national level
- Insufficient information about monitoring results at the school level
- Results are too general
- Lack of practical information that I can use
- Complex/unclear presentation of results in reports
- Lack of support from the school administration
- Insufficient discussion among the school's teaching staff
- No practical obstacles arise
- Other: _____

V. ATTITUDES TOWARD MONITORING

1. To what extent do the monitoring results reflect students' actual achievements?

- 1 – do not reflect at all (do not match my own observations)
- 2 – reflect only slightly (cover only a few specific aspects, but not objective reality)
- 3 – partially reflect (show only general trends, but do not take all factors into account)
- 4 – mostly reflect (mostly align with my own observations)
- 5 – fully reflect (accurately show students' academic achievement and confirm my own observations)

2. In your opinion, how effective are monitoring efforts in improving the quality of education?

- 1 – completely ineffective (have no impact on educational practice)
- 2 – ineffective (have almost no practical application)
- 3 – moderately effective (are taken into account only in isolated cases)
- 4 – effective (have a real impact on teaching approaches and curriculum planning)
- 5 – very effective (systematically used to improve the quality of education)

3. In your opinion, how can monitoring results be made more useful for teachers? (optional) _____

Thank you for participating!